

Virtual Reality (VR) Health, Safety, and Prior Experience Screening Survey For Educational Research Use in Schools.

Authors:

Mahmoud Hamash (Corresponding Author)

School of STEM Education, Innovation and Global Studies,
Institute of Education, Dublin City University, Dublin, Ireland

Email: *mahmoud.hamash2@mail.dcu.ie*

Peter Tiernan

School of STEM Education, Innovation and Global Studies,
Institute of Education, Dublin City University, Dublin, Ireland

Email: *peter.d.tiernan@dcu.ie*

About This Survey

This Health, Safety, and Prior Experience Screening Survey is designed to support the ethical, safe, and inclusive participation of students in educational research involving immersive Virtual Reality (VR) technologies.

Immersive VR typically involves the use of a head-mounted display (HMD) that allows users to feel present within a simulated environment and to interact with virtual objects or spaces. While VR can offer valuable learning opportunities, research and manufacturer guidance indicate that some users, particularly children and young people, may experience physical, sensory, or emotional discomfort.

This survey is used to:

- Identify any prior experiences, sensitivities, or conditions that may increase the risk of discomfort or adverse effects
- Support risk minimisation and participant wellbeing

- Enable reasonable adjustments, including non-immersive alternatives
- Uphold ethical principles of informed consent, non-maleficence, and child safeguarding

Participation in immersive VR is voluntary. Students may stop participating or withdraw at any time without penalty and without any negative consequences for their schooling.

This study has received approval from the relevant Research Ethics Committee. All data will be processed in accordance with GDPR, institutional ethics policies, and child safeguarding requirements.

Participant Information

Student Name: _____

Age: _____ years

Gender (optional):

Male Female Prefer not to say Other / self-describe _____

Section A: Prior Experience with Virtual Reality (VR)

1. Has the student previously used Virtual Reality with a headset?

- No
- Yes – once
- Yes – occasionally
- Yes – frequently

2. What type of VR experience has the student used? (tick all that apply)

- Educational

- Gaming
- Simulation (e.g. science lab, driving, flight)
- Entertainment
- Not applicable

3. Has the student ever felt unwell during or shortly after using VR?

- No
- Mild discomfort
- Moderate discomfort
- Severe discomfort

4. If discomfort was experienced, did it include any of the following?

- Nausea
- Dizziness
- Headache
- Eye strain
- Disorientation
- Anxiety or panic
- Fatigue
- None of the above

Section B: Gaming and Screen-Based Experience

5. Does the student regularly play digital or video games (console, PC, mobile, or VR)?

- No
- Occasionally
- Frequently

6. Has the student ever experienced physical or emotional discomfort while gaming?

- No
- Yes

7. If yes, did this include any of the following?

- Motion sickness
- Dizziness or nausea
- Headaches or eye strain
- Sensory overload (visual or sound)
- Anxiety, distress, or panic
- Difficulty stopping or distress when gaming ended
- Not applicable

8. Has the student ever stopped using a game or digital experience due to discomfort or distress?

- No
- Yes

Section C: Motion Sickness History

9. Before the age of 12, how often did the student feel sick, nauseated, or dizzy during the following activities?

Activity	Never	Rarely	Sometimes	Frequently
Car travel	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
Bus / train	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
Boats / ferries	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
Swings / roundabouts	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>

Activity	Never	Rarely	Sometimes	Frequently
Rollercoasters / funfair rides	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>

10. Since the age of 12, has the student experienced motion sickness?

- Never
 - Rarely
 - Sometimes
 - Frequently
-

Section D: Medical, Sensory, and Psychological Considerations

11. Has the student experienced or been diagnosed with any of the following? (tick all that apply)

- Photosensitive epilepsy or seizures
- Blackouts, dizziness, or loss of awareness triggered by flashing lights or patterns
- Migraines or light sensitivity
- Heart condition
- Sensory sensitivities (e.g. noise, visuals, movement)
- Anxiety or panic-related conditions
- Neurodivergent sensory processing differences
- Other medical condition
- None of the above

12. Does the student have any implanted medical devices (e.g. pacemaker) that could be affected by electronic or wireless

equipment?

- No
- Yes

13. Are there any phobias, fears, or sensitivities that may be triggered by immersive VR (e.g. heights, enclosed spaces, loud sounds)?

- No
 - Yes
-

Section E: Overall Risk Awareness

14. Based on the information above, does the parent/guardian believe immersive VR use may cause discomfort or distress for the student?

- No
 - Possibly
 - Yes
-

Participant Acknowledgement and Consent

Parent / Guardian Consent

- I have read and understood the information provided about the use of immersive Virtual Reality (VR) in this research study.
- I understand that immersive VR may cause physical, sensory, or emotional effects such as dizziness, nausea, eye strain, fatigue, or anxiety.
- I confirm that the information provided in this screening survey is accurate to the best of my knowledge.
- I understand that my child's participation in immersive VR is voluntary and that they may stop or withdraw at any time without penalty.

I understand that if this screening identifies potential risk, my child may be advised not to use a VR headset and will be offered an alternative activity.

I understand that all information collected will be treated confidentially and processed in line with GDPR and institutional research ethics policies.

I give consent for my child to participate in this research study subject to the outcomes of this screening survey.

Parent / Guardian Name: _____

Signature: _____

Date: ____ / ____ / ____

Student Assent

I have been told what Virtual Reality is and what I will be asked to do in this study.

I understand that I can stop using VR or withdraw at any time if I feel uncomfortable or change my mind.

I know that saying no will not affect me at school in any way.

I agree to take part in this study.

Student Name: _____

Signature: _____

Date: ____ / ____ / ____

Researcher Declaration

I confirm that the study was explained clearly and in an age-appropriate manner and that questions were answered before consent and assent were obtained.

Researcher Name: _____

Signature: _____

Date: ____ / ____ / ____